

FEATURES OF ADOBE FLASH

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics Student:
Khairiyeva Shahnoza Saydulla qizi.

Abstract: In this article, you will be acquainted with the scope of the Adobe Flash program, its capabilities, file-set extensions.

Key words: multimedia, macromedia, adobe, browser, windows, program

Currently, one of the important tasks is to create dynamic visual aids for the subjects be taught, relying on the animation effects of educational materials. The Adobe (Macromedia) Flash series products provide very convenient and extensive opportunities for solving such problems.

Flash technology (SWF) is a technology based on the use of vector graphics in the Small Web Format (formerly Shock Wave Flash) format. Although this format is not one of the most effective graphic formats, SWF format allows users to use graphics processing tools with unlimited graphics capabilities and the result in Web browsers and the necessary editors. Another advantage of Flash technology is its flexibility, which means that this format can be used on all platforms (MacOS-based Macintosh computers or Windows-based computers). Another convenient possibility is that the images created with it can be not only animated, but also enriched with interactive elements and sound and controlled by programming.

The flexibility of Flash technology and the ability to create interactive multimedia programs have caused debate among many Web designers and allowed it to increase in popularity.

The development of computer technology is compact and elegant, making it possible to create user-friendly mobile applications. These built-in programs also work with major web browsers. Adobe (Macromedia) has created one of these programs, the Flash package, which allows you to use the full range of technical WEB-design tools.

Currently, 50 percent of sites in the world are partially or completely created on the base of Flash technology. Designers are attracted by the new possibilities of creating graphics in Adobe Flash, while professional creators are able to create applications using scripts, forms and server capabilities. Macromedia Flash creates memorable Web sites. With this tool, you can combine vector graphics and raster images, add sounds, create animations, and more. Adobe Flash comes in handy when creating web pages, and has the ability to import. At the same time, this program has

options for working with active elements and programming. Mainly small animation files (clips) in adobe Flash program, Internet pages, electronic manuals and files created in Flash program stand out for their originality, simplicity of operation, complexity of creation, speed, multimedia equipment and small size.

Flash has the following capabilities:

- **The size of the created file is small and the Flash program can be loaded quickly from the network.** Because Flash uses a vector format, it compresses files and therefore reduces file size;
- **A cross-browser dependency**, i.e. Flash works with IE, NNs;
- **The power of control language.** A special programming language is used in Adobe Flash, in which the user can use the features convenient for his page, that is, arrays, repetition, formulas and conditions can be fully used;
- **Beauty.** In Flash, even a simple sphere or arbitrary shape can be depicted with very beautiful colors.
- **Convenience.** Flash can be used by any student who knows basic drawing;
- **The number of executors.** If the user needs graphics, sound and small files, then Flash has no equal. Flash software works for Windows 95/98/NT/2000.

Conclusion

Implementation of the idea of educational reforms depends on a number of important factors. Among them, there are such complex problems that it is inappropriate to talk about the effect of fundamental changes without successfully solving these problems. The process of solving such problems is the development of an electronic education system and the creation of electronic information resources using the Adobe Flash program, among the knowledge provided on the base of new pedagogical technologies.

List of references

1. Aripov M., Madрахimov A. Informatics, information technologies Textbook. T. TDYUI, 2004. 194 p.
2. Mo'minov B.B. Pedagogical software creation technology. Bukhara-2010.
3. Begimkulov U. Sh. Organization of pedagogical education in the environment of modern information technologies. Journal "Pedagogical Education", No. 1, 2004. 25-26 p.
4. <https://ru.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flash>
5. <http://www.actionscripts.org/>

6. Mo'minov B. Informatics. Tashkent is the "City of Thought". 2014 290-292 p.

